

F₂ distribution of TMR, TSV, and SLW in the cross of Guichao 2/82-856F₂.

72.52% for SLW, 66.19% for TMR, and 33.84% for TSV.

This suggests that SLW and TSV had multigenic and additive actions and that

TMR was controlled by some major genes and a small number of dominant genes with cumulative and unequal effect. ■

Photoperiod sensitivity of traditional rice variety of Andamans

S. Singh and T. Ram, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Port Blair 744101, India

Local rice variety C14-8 occupies more than 50% of the rice area in Andamans. We compared its photoperiod sensitivity

with the moderate photoperiod sensitivity of modern variety CR1009 at 12° N lat. and 92-94° E long. The crops were sown on the 10th d of each month for 1 yr.

CR1009 sown in Oct flowered in 100 d. When sown in Mar and Apr, it flowered in 130 d (Fig. 1). C14-8 sown in Nov flowered in 115 d. When sown in Dec, it flowered in 341 d, the difference being 226 d. The basic vegetative phase

1. Days to flowering of rice varieties sown in different months.

2. Variation in daylength and temperature during different months in Port Blair, India.

of CR1009 was about 65 d and that of C14-8 80 d. The photoperiod-sensitive phase was about 30 and 226 d, respectively.

The marked difference in flowering durations with month of sowing is attributed mainly to response to varying daylengths in different months (Fig. 2). Variation in days to flowering was caused by difference in vegetative lag phase only. The basic vegetative, reproductive, and ripening phases were constant in both varieties.

C14-8 is highly sensitive to slight variations in daylength, indicating strong photoperiod sensitivity. ■

Association of rice ratooning ability and vigor with grain yield

M. Subramanian and A. Ramalingam, Agricultural Botany Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute (ACRI), Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India

We evaluated rice ratooning ability, vigor, and yield in 22 rice cultivars during 1987 wet season. The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. At harvest, the main crop was cut leaving a 15 cm culm. The stubble was irrigated 3 d after harvest and 40 kg N/ha applied 7 d after harvest.

Ratoon vigor was assessed as 1 = extra vigorous, 5 = intermediate or normal, 9 = very weak. A ratoon rating (RR) was calculated as

$$RR = (1 - [0.1 \text{ ratoon vigor}]^{\text{av number of ratoon tillers/plant}})$$